

Provision of Settlements in the Regions of the Near North with Educational and Health Care Institutions

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Abstract

Using the example of four regions of the Near North of Russia, the prevalence of educational and health care institutions in 22 thousand settlements (SS) of different status and size is analysed. The proportion of the population that has access to comprehensive or at least basic services at their place of residence is estimated. The dynamics of the population size is analysed depending on the provision of settlements with these institutions during the last intercensal period. The article is based on data collected from open sources on the availability of educational and health care institutions, as well as on population data based on the results of the All-Russian Census of Population of 2010 and 2020.

In spite of the fact that educational institutions are available in 7.4% of populated areas, and health care institutions in 14%, the majority of the population (even without considering those living in large cities) is provided with basic services at their place of residence. Calculations are given for the provision of settlements of different sizes and administrative status with all types of educational and health care institutions.

Despite the optimisation of the network of institutions, the provision of the population with them did not decrease during the 2010s, as the process of population decline and its concentration in larger settlements proceeded at an equally rapid pace. Regardless of the provision of settlements with educational and health care organisations, the reduction in their population was very significant.

Keywords

educational institutions, healthcare institutions, population, settlements, the Near North, social services

JEL codes: H42, J11, I18, I28, R53

Introduction

The article analyses the population and settlements (SS) of the Vologda, Kostroma, Kirov, and Yaroslavl regions. These regions, traditionally belonging to the Non-Black Earth Zone of Russia, are also territories of the so-called Near North. In general, they, like other regions of Russia, are characterised by the concentration of population in large cities: more than half of the residents of these regions lived in six settlements with a population of over 100 thousand people at the end of 2021.

Outside of large cities, the population is concentrated in small and medium-sized cities, which are most often regional centres or centres of urban districts. Rural settlement is sparsely populated; many settlements (a third, according to the 2020 All-Russian Census of Population (ARCP)) are uninhabited, and their number is growing. Over the past decades, there has been widespread depopulation, a migration outflow of the population both from peripheral territories to the capitals and their suburbs, and beyond the regions.

Along with the reduction in population, there is a process of optimising the network of educational and health care institutions, most often leading to a reduction in their number, a decrease in the complexity of the services they provide, and possibly resulting in reduced availability of these services for the population, especially those living in rural areas.

To a large extent, these processes are connected with the shortage of specialists in the countryside; attempts to mitigate the consequences of this problem led to the implementation of the “County Council Doctor” and “County Council Teacher” programmes, but these only partially helped to resolve it.

It is unclear, however, what is the trigger for the changes taking place: is the population decline leading to the need to close social institutions, or is the contraction of social infrastructure accelerating population decline in communities that have lost their schools or outpatient clinics?

The principles of forming a network of educational and health care institutions assume that the larger the settlement, the more extensive the “set” of relevant institutions, and the residents of this settlement have the opportunity to receive a more comprehensive range of services. However, in a country as vast as Russia, with sharp contrasts in the settlement system, these rules do not always apply.

The aim of the study is to analyse the availability of educational and health care institutions in settlements of different status and size using the example of four regions of the Near North of Russia, to estimate the proportion of the population that has the opportunity to receive comprehensive or at least basic services at their place of residence, and to track the dynamics of the population depending on the provision of settlements with these institutions over the last intercensal period.

Literature Review

The provision of the population with education and health services in Russia is studied within the framework of the geography of the public service sector, or the territorial organisation of the service sector. All types of social infrastructure, including educational and health care institutions, are characterised by a hierarchy of services (Zubarevich 2013), and the concentration of institutions in administrative centres. This hierarchy implies the

development of integrated public service centres represented by large cities (Egorov and Nikolaev 2017), alongside the absence of a significant range of services and varying degrees of their accessibility – including transport – for the population of the surrounding territories.

The relationship between the transformation of the settlement system, its compression, and the dynamics of the network of social service institutions for the population is beyond doubt (Zubarevich 2013). However, detailed studies conducted at the level of rural settlements and populated areas are extremely rare. Interest in such studies is partly connected with the ongoing changes in the rural settlement network and the awareness of their irreversibility, as well as the need to optimise the network of social service institutions for the population.

In relation to the network of educational institutions, this optimisation was most actively carried out in the 2000s (Order of the Ministry... 2002), and in relation to the network of health care institutions – in the 2010s (Order of the Ministry... 2016). As in other countries, the optimisation of the network of educational institutions caused the greatest public resonance. It was carried out in accordance with standards that provide for the territorial (transport or walking) accessibility of institutions for the population, the minimum level of provision of these institutions for municipalities depending on population size and the degree of urbanisation, and, in the case of rural educational institutions, their capacity.

Long-term studies on school network optimisation (Egorov and Nikolaev 2022), including those focused on specific regions, show that as a result, the enrolment of rural schools increases (Nikolaev and Egorov 2022), and the efficiency of using educational infrastructure improves. However, the requirements for transport accessibility of institutions for the population are often violated. It is evident that optimisation cannot be adequate without addressing the issue of transport accessibility of both schools and health care institutions (Zelenyuk 2019). Therefore, the objectives of research and their practical aspects are often associated with determining the transport accessibility of social infrastructure institutions for the populations of different settlements.

Social infrastructure institutions (schools, medical institutions) are considered the most important links in the organisation of space at the grassroots level and “fundamental elements for maintaining life in a populated area” (Vikhrev et al. 2016), performing important functions in providing social services to the population. According to research, lower-level settlement centres that fulfil these functions are less likely to lose their population (Tkachenko et al. 2019). Employment in social institutions in rural areas plays an increasingly important – often key – role in the employment structure of the population (Alekseev and Safronov 2015); according to various estimates, it exceeds the share of those employed in agriculture (Averkiewa 2016).

The consequences of long-term population decline in rural areas are associated with increased costs for providing education, health care, and other services in small settlements, the disappearance of grassroots service delivery centres, and the resulting increase in the distance that the population must travel to larger centres (Clout 1972).

The process of optimising the network of schools and hospitals has been under way for a long time in many European countries, the USA, Canada, and Australia (Lonsdale and Holmes 1981; Planey et al. 2024; Mullens et al. 2024). The need to ensure equality in the provision of basic social services to the population everywhere comes into conflict with the economic efficiency of maintaining a network of institutions (Amcoff 2012; Lehtonen 2021). These questions continue to attract the interest of many researchers.

Methodology and data used

The article analyses information on all populated areas in the Vologda, Kostroma, Kirov, and Yaroslavl regions. Their total number, according to the 2020 All-Russian Census of Population (ARCP-2020), is 22 thousand, of which 7.3 thousand were uninhabited. Of the total number of populated areas at the beginning of 2024, six are cities with a population of 100 thousand or more, one is a medium-sized city, 49 are small cities, and 66 are urban-type settlements; the remainder are rural settlements.

Based on the objectives of the study, settlements were classified according to the presence of administrative status: regional capitals (all large cities with a population of over 100 thousand people), urban settlements within a district/region (28, of which two have a population of over 100 thousand), centres of urban/municipal districts or municipal regions (104), and centres of rural settlements (586).

During the period under study, many transformations were carried out at the municipal level in Russia, primarily related to the abolition and consolidation of rural settlements. The unification of educational organisations also continued, often accompanied by their complete closure. Therefore, settlements that lost their status as rural settlement centres between 2011 and 2023 due to the abolition or merger of such settlements (155 in total across the four regions) were also identified. The number of rural settlements that do not hold any status but are inhabited, according to the 2020 All-Russian Census of Population, was 13.8 thousand.

The source of population data for each locality was the 2010 and 2020 All-Russian Census of Population. Population censuses are the only official source containing such information; the data were provided by Rosstat upon request.

As far as we are aware, there is no publicly accessible register in Russia of social institutions of various types detailed down to the level of individual settlements. Information on the social infrastructure of settlements was collected in relation to the availability of relevant institutions.

Educational organisations included general education institutions – secondary (SES), general (GES), and primary (PES) education; preschool institutions (PSI); and institutions of additional education such as evening schools, art schools, sports schools, boarding schools, schools for children with disabilities, psycho-neurological institutions, etc.

Training according to preschool education programmes is available both in separate institutions and in preschool groups organised within schools. However, it is extremely difficult to clearly distinguish between these forms of provision – a kindergarten may be located within a school building or in a separate space.

In this study, the focus was not on identifying the presence of a separate institution (e.g., a kindergarten), but rather on assessing the possibility of delivering the relevant programme within a given settlement.

Information on the prevalence of vocational education institutions was also collected, but it was not analysed in this study due to the concentration of such institutions in the largest and most prestigious settlements.

Information about educational institutions was collected on the basis of data posted on the websites of district (regional) education departments/offices (most often under the section “Subordinate Organisations”), as well as from other open sources – primarily the websites of the institutions themselves, in the section “Basic Information about the Educational Organisation”. In particular, the websites of these institutions provided information about the availability and location of branches of educational organisations and the presence of preschool groups.

The information was verified using Yandex Maps (<https://yandex.ru/maps/>), and in some cases, 2GIS (<https://2gis.ru>), as well as the Rusprofile website (<https://www.rusprofile.ru>), which contains up-to-date data on active organisations, the dates of their liquidation, successor and predecessor organisations, and other open data sources.

Health care institutions included Central District Hospitals (CDH) and their branches (District Hospitals, DH), medical outpatient clinics, general practitioners' offices (GPs), and feldsher-obstetric stations (or feldsher-midwife points, FAPs). Information was collected from the websites of Central Regional Hospitals (most often under the section "Subordinate Organisations" or from the "Licences for Medical Activities") and verified using Yandex Maps (<https://yandex.ru/maps/>), in some cases 2GIS (<https://2gis.ru>), the OnlineZdrav portal (<https://onlinezdrav.ru/>), and other open sources.

Unfortunately, these sources do not provide information on whether a healthcare institution – primarily lower-level ones such as FAPs – has permanent and adequately equipped medical staff, or whether it operates on an irregular basis. Thus, information about the presence or absence of a FAP and its functionality in a specific locality is the least reliable and quite difficult to verify. The number of healthcare institutions did not include medical offices located in schools and kindergartens.

When collecting data, the main source of information was the websites of government agencies, reflecting the existence of these institutions as of mid-2024. However, this information had to be verified using at least one additional source. Exceptions were made only for FAPs, for which only data from government agency websites were used, as these institutions are not always adequately represented on maps.

If a given locality had several institutions providing social services with similar functions (e.g. two secondary schools; a secondary and a basic school; a hospital branch and an outpatient clinic), this was not taken into account. The primary concern was the presence of at least one institution of the given type. Immediate accessibility, availability of places, and staffing levels were also not assessed, as these are subjects of a separate study.

The analysis focused on the presence in a particular settlement (SS) of institutions offering a higher level of education or, in the case of healthcare organisations, providing the most comprehensive services. For example, if a branch of the Central Regional Hospital was present, the presence of a FAP was no longer considered significant.

Russian studies of the public service sector also analyse information on the availability of cultural institutions (such as houses of culture, libraries, and village clubs), post offices, and stationary trade facilities (Zubarevich 2013; Tkachenko and Fomkina 2016). In our work, this information was neither collected nor analysed, due both to its limited availability in open sources and, more importantly, to the secondary nature of the services provided compared to education and health care.

Key Results

Educational institutions and organizations

According to the data collected for all settlements in the Vologda, Kostroma, Kirov, and Yaroslavl regions (excluding six large cities, which have a well-developed network of educational institutions throughout), only a small proportion of settlements had educational institutions (Table 1).

Table 1. Settlements* by population size and the presence of general education institutions (the highest level available) and additional education institutions, 2010 and 2021

Presence/absence of an institution	number of SS	population size	
		thousand people	average, persons
2010			
Secondary (middle, general education) school	503	1610.3	3201
Basic school	402	174.1	433
Primary school	82	32.8	400
Kindergarten	107	51.3	480
Institution of additional education	131	1216.2	9284
There are no educational institutions	15974	466.5	29
Total SS	17068	2335.1	137
2021			
Secondary (middle, general education) school	503	1395	2773
Basic school	402	137.4	342
Primary school	82	28.3	345
Kindergarten	107	53.3	498
Institution of additional education	131	1052.1	8031
There are no educational institutions	13551	363.9	27
Total SS	14645	1977.9	135

Sources: data from the All-Russian Census of Population for 2010 and 2020, websites of municipal education departments, websites of the Central Regional Hospitals and other open sources on the Internet. *Note:* * excluding cities with a population of more than 100 thousand people and settlements without population as of the dates of the 2010 and 2020 All-Russian Census of Population.

Relative to the total number of inhabited settlements (i.e., those with a non-zero population)¹ at the end of 2010, such institutions were present in 6.4% of populated areas in 2024; if we consider the number of inhabited settlements in 2021 – which had decreased compared to 2010 – this proportion rises to 7.4%.

It is known that since the early 2000s, the reduction in the number of educational institutions through various processes (merger, closure, lowering the level of the institution, integration of kindergartens into primary or secondary schools, etc.) has proceeded at a fairly active pace in peripheral territories (Egorov and Nikolaev 2022).

Institutions of additional education (such as children’s creativity centres, music schools, etc.) were available in less than 1% of settlements.

At the same time, due to the presence and retention of educational institutions in the largest settlements, fewer than 20% of residents in all settlements (excluding large cities) lived in settlements without educational institutions. Approximately 70% of the population

¹ In Russia, according to the 2020 All-Russian Census of Population, there are almost 25 thousand, or 16.1% of settlements “without population”, with zero residents.

lived in settlements where there was a secondary (middle, general education) school, and this proportion – like the share of the population living in settlements with other types of educational institutions – is gradually increasing.

Institutions of additional education were located in a small number of large settlements; nevertheless, even excluding large cities, more than half of the population had the opportunity to access their services in their place of residence.

Residents of more than half of the settlements with a population over 500 have the opportunity to attend secondary school within their settlement (Figure 1). In villages with fewer residents that have educational institutions, these are most often primary schools. The majority of settlements with a population of 250 or fewer no longer had educational institutions; settlements with a population of less than 100 were served by educational institutions in only 0.4% of cases.

Despite the transformation of the network of educational institutions in the 2010s, calculations show that the average population in rural settlements with schools of different levels and preschool education institutions decreased between 2010 and 2021. This is primarily due to widespread population decline in the vast majority of settlements, especially rapid in rural peripheral areas (Karachurina and Mkrtchyan 2023).

At the same time, the rate of population decline is only slightly influenced by the availability of educational institutions: in settlements with a secondary school in 2024, the population decreased by 15.4% during the intercensal period 2011–2021, while across all settlements excluding large cities, it fell by 17.6%. The population of rural settlements with a primary school decreased by 26.7% during this period, compared to a 25.5% decrease in rural settlements with no educational institutions at all by 2024.

Figure 1. Accessibility of educational institutions in your locality (highest level of services provided) by the size of the SS, %

It is important to acknowledge that these comparisons are seriously limited by the lack of detailed information on the dynamics of the institutional network over the specified period and provide only a superficial indication of their possible impact on population trends.

An interesting feature is the small (though symbolic, given the widespread decline) population growth in settlements where the only educational institutions are kindergartens. Analysis shows that this growth is driven by settlements in the suburbs of a rare circle of large cities and regional centres. We believe that the limited educational infrastructure in suburban communities with kindergartens is linked, firstly, to the relocation of families with children of the relevant age to these communities, and, secondly, to the need to preserve and develop the network of these institutions due to stricter requirements for their accessibility.

In formally rural suburbs of large cities, these may be residential complexes located on the lands of rural settlements, where developers can construct separate social institutions. However, in practice, these are often private kindergartens, which are not accessible to all residents of these settlements.

It should be noted that the distribution of settlements with basic and primary schools, as well as kindergartens, by average population size shows little difference. Larger settlements are characteristic of those with secondary schools. As research indicates (Vikhrev et al. 2016), these institutions are the key link in the formation of settlement networks on the periphery, at least in the analysed regions of the Near North. Institutions of additional education were almost always located in regional centres, i.e., in the largest populated areas.

Healthcare institutions

Like the network of educational institutions, the system of healthcare institutions is undergoing significant transformation (Vasilyeva 2012). In the four regions studied, only 1% of rural settlements had a central regional hospital or its branch; outpatient clinics, FAPs, and general practitioners were distributed much more frequently (Table 2). However, 88% of municipalities with a non-zero population in 2010, and 86% in 2021, had no healthcare facilities by 2024. As with educational institutions, their coverage increased slightly due to the reduction in the number of inhabited settlements in 2021.

Table 2. Settlements* by population size and the presence of general education institutions (the highest level available) and additional education institutions, 2010 and 2021

Presence/absence of an institution	number of SS	population size	
		thousand people	average, people per SS
2010			
Central district hospital, interdistrict hospital	100	1092.9	10929
Branch of the Central Regional Hospital	49	166.9	3406
Outpatient clinic	244	316.6	1297
FAP/GP	1667	436.1	262
There are no institutions	15008	322.6	21
Total	17068	2335.1	137

Presence/absence of an institution	number of SS	population size	
		thousand people	average, people per SS
2021			
Central district hospital, interdistrict hospital	100	950.1	9501
Branch of the Central Regional Hospital	49	136.7	2790
Outpatient clinic	244	280.9	1151
FAP/GP	1667	333.4	200
There are no institutions	12585	276.8	25
Total	14645	1977.9	135

Sources: data from the All-Russian Census of Population for 2010 and 2020, websites of municipal education departments, websites of the Central Regional Hospitals and other open sources on the Internet. Note: * excluding cities with a population of more than 100 thousand people and settlements without population as of the dates of the 2010 and 2020 All-Russian Census of Population.

In most populated areas with a population exceeding 3,000 people, there is usually a central district hospital, metropolitan hospital, or one of their branches (Figure 2); in rural settlements with populations between 1,000 and 3,000, there is typically an outpatient clinic; in smaller rural settlements, medical services are generally limited to the capabilities of a first aid post or, much less frequently, a general practitioner. Overall, most settlements with

Figure 2. Accessibility of educational institutions in your locality (highest level of services provided) by size of the SS, %

populations over 100 have these low-level institutions; in less populated settlements, even these services are usually unavailable.

Outside of large cities, less than 15% of the population in the regions under consideration lived in settlements without any healthcare facilities. Local healthcare institutions (FAPs) are more widespread than primary healthcare institutions and kindergartens, as they require fewer personnel and, apparently, the standards for their operation are less strict. Furthermore, the collected data do not allow us to determine whether a particular FAP is staffed with permanent medical personnel (often, on the websites of the Central Regional Hospitals, the position of paramedic or nurse was listed as vacant) or whether it operates on a temporary schedule. The provision of peripheral territories with medical personnel is chronically insufficient (Andreeva and Karachurina 2021).

The average population of settlements both with and without healthcare institutions decreased everywhere, except in settlements without any institutions. This, as with settlements lacking educational institutions, is primarily a consequence of population decline and the reduction in the number of inhabited villages and hamlets during the last intercensal period. The smaller the population of a settlement, the less comprehensive the services its residents can receive at the place of residence. The fastest population decline was observed in rural settlements with FAPs or primary care physicians. This may be because such institutions tend to remain in communities with a clearly predominantly elderly population, which faces the highest mortality risks. However, naturally, this does not resolve the problem of the extinction of such villages and towns.

Administrative status of settlements

The administrative status of settlements is closely related to their population size, as it is primarily granted to the largest settlements. Accordingly, outside of large cities, institutions providing the most comprehensive services to the population are located mainly in district centres, urban district centres, and urban settlements (Table 3). The table displays only the institutions offering the most comprehensive services: for example, if a settlement has both a secondary school and a primary school, or a central district hospital and an outpatient clinic, only the presence of the secondary school and central district hospital is recorded.

Among the lower centres – centres of rural settlements as of mid-2024 – 42.7% had a secondary school, 31.1% had a basic school, and in 6.7% the highest level of education available was only primary school or kindergarten. Surprisingly, 19.6% of rural settlement centres did not have any educational institutions. The presence of a branch of the Central Regional Hospital in a rural settlement centre was quite rare; only 4.6% of such local centres had one. Outpatient clinics were present in 27%, while in 62.3% of rural settlements with this administrative status, medical care was limited to the capabilities of a FAP or GP. However, healthcare facilities were entirely absent in only 6.1% of these lower centres.

If we consider separately the settlements that lost their status as rural settlement centres between 2011 and 2023 (excluding cases where status was lost due to the formation of municipal districts), their provision with educational and healthcare institutions is significantly worse. In 63.6% of these former centres, there were no educational institutions, no branches of the Central Regional Hospital, and outpatient clinics were found

only in isolated cases. However, 83.4% of rural settlements in this category had a FAP or GP, and only 13.2% of these former rural settlement centres lacked healthcare facilities altogether.

Among ordinary settlements (those without current or previous administrative status), over 90% did not have any educational or healthcare institutions. Schools and outpatient clinics were found only in a few of the largest non-status settlements, while FAPs or GPs were somewhat more widespread, present in 8.6% of ordinary rural communities.

Table 3. Healthcare and educational institutions* in SS of different administrative status**, number of SS

	Central Regional Hospital, Municipal Hospital and branches	Out-patient clinic	FAP and GP	There are no educational institutions
District and municipal centers				
Secondary school	102 (98.1)	2 (1.9)
Urban settlements				
Secondary school	14 (53.8)	9 (34.6)
BES	2 (7.7)	1 (3.8)
Rural settlement centers				
Secondary school	24 (4.1)	122 (20.7)	101 (17.1)	3 (0.5)
BES	3 (0.5)	28 (4.8)	148 (25.1)	3 (0.5)
PES and PSI	...	8 (1.4)	27 (4.6)	4 (0.7)
There are no educational institutions	...	3 (0.5)	89 (15.1)	26 (4.4)
Former centers of rural settlements				
Secondary school	...	4 (2.6)	8 (5.3)	...
GES	...	1 (0.7)	29 (19.2)	...
PES and PSI	13 (8.6)	...
There are no educational institutions	76 (50.3)	20 (13.2)
SS without administrative status				
Secondary school	3 (0.02)	38 (0.3)	56 (0.4)	17 (0.1)
GES	...	14 (0.1)	156 (1.1)	16 (0.1)
PES and PSI	...	6 (0.04)	98 (0.7)	32 (0.2)
There are no educational institutions	1 (0.01)	4 (0.03)	872 (6.3)	12465 (90.5)

Sources: data from the All-Russian Census of Population for 2010 and 2020, websites of municipal education departments, websites of the Central Regional Hospitals and other open sources on the Internet; Population of the Russian Federation by municipalities. Statistical bulletin. M.: Rosstat, 2023. *Notes:* shares (%) of all SS of this class are given in brackets; * if there are several institutions in the SS, the institution providing the most comprehensive services is listed; ** excluding cities with a population of over 100 thousand people.

Grouping of settlements by the presence of educational and healthcare institutions and population dynamics

Information on the availability of educational and healthcare institutions formed the basis for a typology of settlements in the aforementioned regions according to their level of social service provision. Apart from large cities, where the population is comprehensively served by social institutions, the following types of settlements can be distinguished:

- integrated social service centres: these have a secondary school, a kindergarten, a central district hospital or its branch, and almost always institutions of additional education; some also include vocational education institutions;
- inter-settlement centres: these contain a secondary (rarely primary) school, preschool education (either in a dedicated preschool institution or within a school), a branch of a hospital or medical clinic, and occasionally additional education institutions. The key element of social infrastructure in this settlement type is the secondary school, as their number in the rural hinterland of the studied regions is limited, and the presence of a secondary school implies regular travel between settlements;
- settlements with 2-3 social institutions: typically a primary or elementary school/preschool educational institution, together with an outpatient clinic or first-aid post;
- settlements with only one institution: most often a FAP, though in rare cases this may be an orphanage, boarding school, care home for the elderly, or similar;
- settlements without any relevant social institutions.

Settlements with no population recorded in the 2020 All-Russian Census of Population were categorised as a separate type. The administrative status of a settlement was not considered in this typology but was included in the subsequent analyses. The structure of the collected data enables separate examination of settlements based on the presence or absence of any type of social institution, as well as their administrative status.

The identified settlement types differ in population size (Table 4); larger settlements generally have a more comprehensive range of educational and healthcare institutions. However, integrated centres offering a full suite of basic services can have a similar population size to settlements with only one institution or none at all. This is explained by the fact that the latter are often located close to large cities or regional centres (such as in suburban areas), where residents regularly travel to access corresponding social services. In the case of schools, for example, such a “positional” factor (Egorov 2022) facilitates the transportation of students to larger centres.

A less common situation that reduces the need for basic educational and healthcare institutions is the presence of so-called rural agglomerations, where these institutions are located in one rural settlement or dispersed among several, sometimes quite sizeable, settlements. Numerous examples of such dispersed (“bush”) settlement forms exist in the Vologda Oblast.

At the same time, rural settlements of relatively small size can be well supplied with social infrastructure institutions due either to their administrative status (as centres of rural settlements) and/or their location at some distance from other settlements, often surrounded by even smaller rural localities. In the absence of larger settlements, these act as grassroots centres for the provision of social services to the population, which inevitably reduces the overall efficiency of service delivery.

Outside large cities, complex centres are most often small towns – predominantly district centres (84%), less frequently urban settlements without district centre status

Table 4. Characteristics of types of SS by population size, 2010 and 2021

	Minimum value	Maximum value	Average value
ARCP-2010			
Comprehensive centers	1448	80921	10425
Inter-settlement centers	355	12224	1579
SS with 2-3 institutions	14	3943	416
SS with 1 institution	0	1439	171
SS without educational and health care institutions	0	3156	22
SS without population	0	284	1
ARCP-2020			
Comprehensive centers	1277	66651	9038
Inter-settlement centers	260	9548	1353
SS with 2-3 institutions	37	6618	352
SS with 1 institution	3	2674	126
SS without educational and health care institutions	1	926	19
SS without population	0	0	0

Sources: data from the All-Russian Census of Population for 2010 and 2020, websites of municipal education departments, websites of the Central Regional Hospitals and other open sources on the Internet. *Note:* SS without population are given for 2021. In 2010, some of them had a population, which is reflected in the corresponding line.

(which are few and typically found on the periphery), and even more rarely large villages serving as rural settlement centres. Inter-settlement centres are most commonly relatively large functioning centres of rural settlements (73%), with small urban settlements comprising a smaller proportion (7%), and former rural settlement centres appearing only in isolated cases. Fewer than 20% of settlements classified as inter-settlement centres have no official status, though these tend to be distinguished by their relatively large size.

Settlements with two or three educational and healthcare institutions most often hold the status of rural settlement centres (42% of the total), or have lost this status (7%). The remaining half of the settlements in this group lack any administrative status. Among settlements with only one institution – sometimes a neuropsychiatric facility, a home for the elderly or disabled, and so forth – only 15% were rural settlement centres (8% retaining and 7% having lost the status), while the rest were ordinary rural settlements. Interestingly, among settlements without any educational or healthcare institutions, there exists a very small number of both former (18) and current (23) rural settlement centres, although overall they represent just 0.2% of settlements in this group.

In the regions studied, approximately half of the population (47.9% in 2010 and 51.7% in 2021) resided in large cities – settlements where a full range of educational and healthcare institutions are available. Despite the growing concentration of population in large cities, their population declined between 2011 and 2021, alongside an almost 10% overall population decrease across all four regions (Table 5).

Table 5. Change in population by selected types of settlements, 2010-2021

	number of SS	Population (thousands of people) as of date	
		ARCP-2010	ARCP-2020
Total population	21988	4483.8	4087.3
Cities with a population of 100 thousand people or more	6	2148.8	2109.4
Comprehensive centers	115	1198.8	1039.4
Inter-settlement centers	231	364.9	312.6
SS with 2-3 institutions	689	286.2	242.6
SS with 1 institution*	1145	195.9	144.3
SS without educational and health care institutions	12465	279.6	239
SS without population	7337	9.6	0

Sources: data from the All-Russian Census of Population for 2010 and 2020, websites of municipal education departments, websites of the Central Regional Hospitals and other open sources on the Internet. *Note:* * including institutions of additional education. SS without population are given for 2021. In 2010, some of them had a population, which is reflected in the corresponding line.

The concentration of population in large cities is well known, but outside these urban centres, the population has been declining rapidly – even in complex centres equipped with adequate basic educational and healthcare institutions. The rate of population decline in these centres was roughly comparable to that in settlements entirely lacking such institutions. This may be explained by the absence of educational and healthcare facilities in rural settlements located in the suburbs of large cities and regional centres, which often experience population growth and increased density. The positive population trends in these suburban settlements partially offset the negative dynamics observed in more remote villages and hamlets.

Conclusions

It appears that the process of optimising the network of educational and healthcare institutions, despite being fairly extensive, is progressing somewhat more slowly than the population decline in peripheral areas. However, this can only be taken as indirect evidence of the continued availability of these services for the populations of the regions studied, as this work only considers the actual presence of institutions in a particular settlement, without accounting for other important factors such as transport accessibility, availability of places, or quality of services. It is also worth noting that during the period under review there was a “downgrading of status”, primarily affecting educational institutions: secondary schools were frequently converted into basic schools, often occurring in the most rapidly depopulating settlements. Nevertheless, the data used in this study do not allow us to clearly determine whether population decline was a cause or a consequence of the transformation of the institutional network. It seems likely that these processes are so interconnected that, much like the transformation of rural settlements (Sheludkov 2020), the contraction of one leads to the degradation and contraction of the other. This issue, however, requires further, more detailed research.

Despite the shrinking network of educational and healthcare institutions, the majority of the population living outside large cities has the opportunity to access these services at their place of residence. This indicates a fairly high formal availability of services even in regions where the rural settlement system is severely deteriorating.

Quite unexpectedly, there was no clear correlation between the availability of educational and healthcare institutions (i.e., provision of relevant services locally) and population dynamics. Even in relatively large settlements, where the population is fully provided with these basic services, the population is declining at a rapid rate, hardly differing from that in settlements lacking such institutions. This is notable given that the presence of these institutions provides a considerable number of public sector jobs (by peripheral territory standards), which should act as a stabilising factor for the population – especially in the smallest settlements, where alternative forms of permanent employment are practically non-existent.

It is important to highlight that residents of remote areas not only lack access to social services but also experience the impoverishment of social space (Fomkina 2017), which further compels them to leave rural localities. The absence of educational institutions plays a similarly adverse role: the smaller the size of a settlement, the more pronounced the outflow of families with children (Mkrtchyan 2024).

As depopulation and migration outflow from peripheral territories to centres – large cities and their suburbs – continue, the network of educational and healthcare institutions will further contract. This process aligns with the spatial compression (Nefyodova and Treyvish 2020) that has been observed in Russia for decades. At the same time, the territorial availability of basic education and health services in peripheral areas is unlikely to decline, although their quality, which is already low, may deteriorate (Eremin 2021). However, this important issue falls outside the scope of the present study.

The “positional” factor – the affiliation of a particular settlement to the suburbs of large, medium, or even small cities, or to cluster forms of rural settlement – is of great significance for the availability of social services. Nevertheless, this crucial topic was only briefly addressed here and warrants further investigation.

Moreover, the consequences of the closure of educational and healthcare institutions in populated areas require detailed study, particularly regarding how such closures affect population dynamics and whether they act as a catalyst for the migration outflow of residents.

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